

SOCIAL WORK DOCTORAL EDUCATION: CURRENT TRENDS AND CHALLENGES

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Current trends in doctoral (PhD) training across the Europe provide evidence on the need to agree on the labor market requests and the content of such training. One of the examples of reaching such consensus can be the one from the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Ireland, where employers, academics, researchers and doctoral students came to an agreement on the knowledge, skills and competences which are needed at modern labour market. A range of documents was adopted at the national level to ensure the above.

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One of the first documents of such kind became Joint skills statement (JSS) of the UK research councils' training requirements for research students [4] which includes a range of core general research skills and transferable skills needed to be formed across all the doctoral students. After the so called Gareth Roberts' the Set for Success report [6] produced in 2002 in the UK, the need for specific focus on transferable skills formation across graduates of higher education institutions was evidenced, due to the gap found between the competences needed by employers and the ones ensured by higher education institutions. After the above report the ten days transferable skills training by higher educational institutions became mandatory in the UK. This had a significant impact on formation of the structure and the content of doctoral training across the UK [2].

The next attempt in finding the compromise between academics and employers was the Concordat to Support Researchers' Career Development signed in 2010. The agreement was signed between the bodies which provide funding for research training as well as various studies and the researchers' employers, and it incorporated clear standards identified by the institution providing job placement for researchers as well as their job descriptions as researchers.

The need for finding solutions to changing market requirements, to adjust the universities' offer to growing need of a wide range of competences building in the UK, resulted into conducting a national wide study which included interviews and focus groups with employers, researchers, practitioners, academics, donors etc. The research outcomes built an evidence to formulate a range of knowledge, competences and

qualifications needed for a successful academic and researcher, to enable his further successful employment and career. Thus, the Researcher Development Framework was developed which became the core framework for research training and career building across the UK.

The Researcher Development Framework (RDF) has been adopted in 2010 in the UK as the tool for those planning their research career, both for Master and Doctoral students in higher educational institutions and for researchers already working and willing to advance their career [3]. As a tool encompassing a range of knowledge, skills and qualifications needed for efficient academic and research career, it also describes a range of competences necessary for developing various stages of research career. Across the UK it is mainly used for planning and ensuring research training for doctoral students, including those studying social work, as well as for their future successful employment. At present this document has been adopted by all the Research Councils of the United Kingdom, the National Association of the UK Universities and other leading research institutions.

According to the RDF, there are four main areas for researchers' development:

1) A - Knowledge and intellectual abilities (includes knowledge, intellectual abilities and techniques to do research);

2) B - Personal effectiveness (includes personal qualities and approach to be an effective researcher);

3) C - Research governance and administration (includes the knowledge of the standards, requirements and professionalism to do research);

4) D - Engagement, influence and impact (includes the knowledge and skills to work with others and ensure the wider impact of research) [3].

Thus, the Researcher Development Framework enables researchers at various stages of their career to find out and to become aware of the following: 'Where are my interests? What am I like doing? How do I develop in those areas which are necessary for the next step in my career? How do I demonstrate my own competences to employers?'

The RDF implementation in research education is ensured by all the higher educational institutions we have studied within our PhD thesis research [1]. Moreover, we were able to find evidence that these requirements are ensured by all the universities willing to create the centres of excellence for doctoral training - Doctoral Training Partnerships, as well as for the rest of universities willing to obtain research funding from the Research Councils UK.

One of the examples of the RDF allocation within the UK universities academic framework is the University of York [5]. Thus, the courses for PhD students, including those studying Social Work, at this University are suggested according to the areas of the Researcher Development Framework. Each of students, having identified the relevant area for own

development, is able to select the courses accordingly to study both within the University and outside the University (in partner institutions). Amongst the courses suggested according to the RDF areas there are the following:

A. Knowledge and intellectual abilities: 'Creativity and problem solving in research', 'Literature search', 'Thesis essentials: using Word', 'Management of research outcomes'.

B. Personal effectiveness: 'Academic writing for doctoral students: introduction', 'Non-academic career: interview', 'Non-academic career: CV and application forms', 'Academic career: interview', 'Academic career: CV and application forms', 'Career planning for doctoral students', 'Using personal potential', 'Using Endnote - bibliography management system', 'Presenting with Power Point', 'Tools for professional development planning', 'Time management tools' etc.

C. Research governance and administration: 'Preparation to confirmation to PhD program enrollment', 'Project management for researchers', 'Students' academic training support', 'Social media for researchers', 'Completing dissertation: process and requirements', 'Preparation to dissertation defense', 'Data protection', «Knowing your (Copy) rights: protecting your own work and re-using other people's', 'Research ethics'.

D. Engagement, influence and impact: 'Open access publications', 'Introduction to blogging', 'Social networks for researchers', 'Introduction to Twitter', 'Advanced blogging', 'Advanced Twittering', 'Creating networks and cooperation: how it can help your research', 'Intercultural cooperation', 'Knowledge dissemination and research', 'Developing an academic poster', 'Getting published in peer-reviewed journals', 'Publications in Arts, Humanitarian and Social Sciences', 'Practicing presentation skills' (based on video discussion), 'Developing presentations', 'Building partnership', 'Training foreign students', 'English and communication workshops for postgraduate foreign students who teach', 'Effective leadership and human resource management', 'Preparing funding proposal: grant application components', 'Community engagement into research', 'Research that matters', 'Writing thesis in Social Sciences'.

Thus using the above RDF as the core tool to develop and to manage the content of research training in the UK higher educational institutions ensured applied character of professional training for researchers, as well as became the framework for their successful career planning. The above specific experience is of particular value for the universities across the Europe and needs to be further studied.

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